

The Rite beats

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Stravinsky's ballet music '*The Rite of Spring*' contains a sequence of accented notes without any apparent pattern, as if the composer was playing tricks with the audience. The sequence occurs during the segment 'Dance of the Girls', although the perplexing pattern must have looked eerily spastic if actually danced to.

The eight measures of the score, excerpted to show only the relevant activity, are displayed below.

The image shows a musical score excerpt with eight measures. The first measure is marked with a blue dot and the number 1. The following seven measures have red dots above them with numbers 10, 12, 18, 21, 25, and 30. The score includes performance instructions like 'non div. arco' and 'sempre sim.'.

The accented notes are marked with a red dot and numbered (in red) relative to the onset (in blue).

The first two measures establish a steady drumbeat, lulling the audience into a false sense of a four-square regularity; but the third measure stresses instead the off-beat 2nd note, jolting with a one-two punch, and then the puzzle unfolds.

The numbered accented sequence off the onset $A = \{10, 12, 18, 21, 25, 30\}$ has kurtosis = 1.7297, very close to the 1.8 value for a uniform distribution; its difference sequence $\{9, 2, 6, 3, 4, 5\}$ has kurtosis = 2.395, not quite the Gaussian's 3. These statistical measures hint a lack of randomness, but offer no insight into how the composer might have chosen his beat sequence.

Let's try and reverse-engineer this sequence.

Consider instead the counts of unaccented gaps relative to the onset; thus $G = \{8, 1, 5, 2, 3, 4\}$. Clearly the linear sequence $\{1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$ is in play here, but recovering the beat sequence itself will require finding the 'constant of integration' so to speak!

Now, a predictable first effort would be (see also the image below)

$$G1 = \{7, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$$

for a note-beat sequence $A1 = \{9, 11, 14, 18, 23, 29\}$

The image shows a musical score excerpt with eight measures. The first measure is marked with a blue dot and the number 1. The following seven measures have red dots above them with numbers 9, 11, 14, 18, 23, and 29. The score includes performance instructions like 'non div. arco' and 'sempre sim.'.

perhaps too mechanical – or predictable – for Stravinsky.

As a second effort, put the third measure accent joltingly on the off-beat 2nd note, as did the composer, but keep the linear gap-note sequence; thus

$G_2 = \{8, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$ giving the beat note-counter $A_2 = \{10, 12, 15, 19, 24, 30\}$; again perhaps too mechanical for the composer (see below).

A musical score in bass clef with a 2/4 time signature. The first measure is marked 'non div. arco' and the second 'sempre sim.'. The score consists of six measures of eighth notes. A blue circle is above the first measure. Red circles are above measures 10, 12, 15, 19, 24, and 30. Below the staff, the numbers 1, 10, 12, 15, 19, 24, and 30 are written in red. The notes are: M1: G2, A2, B2; M2: C3, D3, E3; M3: F3, G3, A3; M4: B3, C4, D4; M5: E4, F4, G4; M6: A4, B4, C5.

A simple way to break this monotony – while giving the audience a (false) respite from the jolts – is to alter the linear gap ordering as (see graphic):

So now the actual gap ordering emerges: $G = \{8, 1, 5, 2, 3, 4\}$ leading exactly to the accented sequence in the music; see below.

A musical score in bass clef with a 2/4 time signature. The first measure is marked 'non div. arco' and the second 'sempre sim.'. The score consists of six measures of eighth notes. A blue circle is above the first measure. Red circles are above measures 10, 12, 18, 21, 25, and 30. Below the staff, the numbers 1, 10, 12, 18, 21, 25, and 30 are written in red. Brackets below the staff indicate gaps: a large bracket from 1 to 10 labeled '8', a small bracket from 10 to 12 labeled '1', a bracket from 12 to 18 labeled '5', a small bracket from 18 to 21 labeled '2', a small bracket from 21 to 25 labeled '3', and a bracket from 25 to 30 labeled '4'.

Of course, we'll never know what process Stravinsky used to generate his unusual beat sequence; however, the process of elimination offered here may not be too farfetched.